

LEGAL BASIS OF ACTIVITY OF CULTURAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. This article talks about the national legislation and legal documents that express the necessity of the activities of cultural institutions in organizing the activities of cultural institutions.

Key words: Culture, cultural institutions, legal basis of activity, national legislation, law, legal document, decision, decree, order.

ПРАВОВЫЕ ОСНОВЫ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ

Аннотация. В данной статье говорится о национальном законодательстве и правовых документах, которые выражают необходимость деятельности учреждений культуры по организации деятельности учреждений культуры.

Ключевые слова: Культура, учреждения культуры, правовые основы деятельности, национальное законодательство, закон, правовой документ, решение, указ, приказ.

It is no exaggeration to say that the Republic of Uzbekistan has reached its current development period on the basis of ensuring the rule of law from the first days of independence.

For example, in a just society, all activities are carried out based on certain laws and regulations. The first task of these laws is to regulate relations in a certain area. The basis of reforms in the field of culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan is first of all laws, decisions and other regulatory documents adopted in the field of culture.

It is necessary to study the legal bases that organize the activities of cultural institutions into three major groups: law, statutory documents and state programs.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, along with all other spheres of society, the development of the sphere of culture also occurs with the nationalistic norms included in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In particular, Article 42 of the Constitution guarantees everyone the freedom of scientific and technical creativity, the right to use cultural achievements.

The state takes care of the cultural, scientific and technical development of the society.

Non-governmental non-profit organization - an organization established on a voluntary basis by individuals and (or) legal entities, which does not make income (profit) the main goal of its activity and does not distribute the received income (profit) among its participants (members). is a self-governing organization.

The state can provide support to special socially useful programs of non-governmental non-profit organizations.

It is not allowed to interfere with the activities of state bodies and their officials in the activities of non-governmental non-profit organizations, as well as the interference of state bodies and their officials with the activities of non-state non-profit organizations.

The interaction of non-governmental non-profit organizations with state bodies is reflected in the following:

- 1) adoption of laws and other regulatory documents on non-governmental non-commercial organizations;
- 2) creation of organizational and legal conditions for registration (re-registration) of non-governmental non-commercial organizations, their operation and termination of their activities;
- 3) to support the implementation of socially beneficial programs of non-governmental non-profit organizations;
- 4) mutual social cooperation with non-governmental non-commercial organizations;
- 5) protection of the rights and legal interests of non-governmental non-commercial organizations.

A non-governmental non-profit organization may join international non-governmental non-profit organizations, establish direct international relations with them, and conclude relevant agreements on cooperation in accordance with legal documents.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, there is a need for advertising services in the regulation of the cultural sector, in particular, in the organization of concerts and performances. In such a situation, a number of norms contained in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Advertising" adopted on December 25, 1998 help to organize the process in a targeted manner. For example, in Article 12 of this law, a situation related to the issue of sponsorship is introduced, and sponsors can participate in creating TV and radio programs, preparing materials for other mass media, organizing theater-concerts, sports events and other events.

In the event that advertising is related to television and radio audiovisual products and sponsorship services are used, information about sponsors should be briefly and clearly recorded at the beginning and end of the program. The sponsor's trademark (service mark) may be displayed next to the sponsor's name (designation). It is not allowed to use the services of sponsors in news

broadcasts. The sponsor does not have the right to interfere in the activities of the sponsored person.

The Law "On Social Partnership" adopted on September 14, 2014 was of great importance in achieving further development of civil society institutions, ensuring the transparency and effectiveness of our ongoing reforms, and strengthening their role.

The Law "On Social Partnership" consists of 5 chapters and 30 articles, Chapter 1 is devoted to general provisions. This chapter describes the purpose of the law, the concept of social partnership, subjects, main principles and areas.

Today, a new era of development has begun in the Republic of Uzbekistan. First of all, the "Strategy of Actions on Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", which defined the five-year activity strategy in the country, became important and created important conditions for the interdependence of all sectors of society. . As a result of this mutual cooperation, the content of the state and society has fundamentally changed, and it has been seen that statehood has become the goal of expressing the rights and interests of citizens and educating a free-thinking human personality based on the world's best experiences, national traditions and values. is doing.

"After the national discussion, the five-year development strategy of Uzbekistan was adopted. Strategy is a real action program of renewal processes. This is a document

is now being consistently implemented. In turn, it made a radical change in the outlook of society members and strengthened their noble goals and aspirations. With these features, the action strategy is a program that determines the scientific-theoretical and methodological bases for development and adaptation to the demands of the fast-paced times in today's information-informed world, where various spiritual threats are increasing.

Adoption of the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on July 28, 2017 "On increasing the efficiency of spiritual and educational work and raising the development of the field to a new level", 2019- of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan On December 31, the role of social and cultural activity in the spiritual renewal of the society began to be more clearly manifested with the decision "On approval of the concept of continuous spiritual education".

In order to increase the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work, to effectively fight against internal and external threats and dangers in the field of spirituality, to strengthen ideological immunity in society, to closely support the activities of state and public organizations in this regard, the Republic of Uzbekistan Decision No. PQ-4307 of the President of May 3, 2019 "On additional measures to increase the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work" was

adopted. According to it, the composition, working body and main directions of activity of the Republican Council of Spirituality and Enlightenment were defined.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 14, 2018 "On the measures to raise the moral, moral and physical maturity of young people and raise the quality of their education system to a new level" - With the decision No. 3907, the mechanisms of promoting socio-cultural activities in the educational system have been put into practice. A comprehensive program of measures consisting of 6 directions was developed and approved to educate young people to be spiritually, morally and physically perfect, to raise the quality of their education system to a new level.

All the laws, decisions, and decrees analyzed above express the need for social and cultural activities in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as serve as a legal basis for creating the necessary conditions for its development. The development of each field is marked by personnel with high professional qualifications, on the one hand, if the quality of education is improved in cultural education based on the integration of science education and production, and on the other hand, these legal sources are full of people's interests. ensures its execution.

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